

Employee at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of Work Involvement on Work Competence at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office. This research was carried out at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office. The type of research is associative quantitative. The sample in this study was 24 employees with ASN and honorary status in the General Section of the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office. The sampling technique in this research uses a saturated sample, where the entire population will be sampled in this research, 24 people. The research results show that Job Involvement has a significant influence on Job Competence as shown by the T-Statistic value of $3,605 > 1.710$ and the P Value of $0.002 < 0.05$. This shows that improvements in Work Engagement can increase Work Competence at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office. The results of the Adjusted R Square value show 0.228 or 22.80%, which means that Work Engagement has a low influence on employee Work Competence while the remaining 77.20% is influenced by other factors that have not been researched.

Keywords: Work Engagement; Job competence

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are an important element for a company to achieve its goals. Human resources are able to plan, organize, direct and mobilize existing factors within the company so that the company can be directed towards the vision that has been set. Human resource management is related to management through organizational activities and operational functions. Regardless of advances in technology and working machines, human factors still play an important role in the success of a company.

Competencies can be used as criteria to determine employee job placement. Employees assigned to certain tasks will know what competencies are required, as well as the path that must be taken to achieve them by evaluating the appropriate competencies. So that the human resource management system is more focused, and employees can be developed to increase their knowledge, skills, expertise, level of competence and work competency, (Maghfiroh, 2015). Competence is the ability to carry out or carry out a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and supported by attitudes that are individual characteristics (Wibowo, 2016).

Every organization always tries to have high hopes for the results of its Work Competencies in the hope of achieving the goals set by the company. If the company has quality resources and has good capabilities, the faster the company will achieve a certain goal.

However, employee job satisfaction in an organization does not always increase, sometimes job satisfaction can also decrease in a company. It is not uncommon for leaders not to know the factors that cause dissatisfaction so that employees feel dissatisfied at

work. Many companies experience problems with employee satisfaction, ranging from lack of incentives, uncomfortable workplaces to problems with employee promotions. If left unchecked, there will be a very high turnover rate. Job satisfaction is often shown by employees by the way they like the job itself and the level of enjoyment they have in carrying out their work. In general, it can be stated that job satisfaction is a feeling of comfort and positive relationships between fellow employees.

Quality human resources can be achieved if the job characteristics received by human resources are in accordance with the employee's capacity. Efforts to provide job characteristics that suit the capacity of human resources are activities that must be carried out by every company so that employee abilities and job satisfaction increase as determined by the company.

Providing job characteristics according to human resource capabilities can be done by providing job characteristics that are in accordance with the employee's capacity to carry out their work within the specified time. One effective way to improve the quality of human resources so they can complete their work well. However, employee job satisfaction is not effective if the job characteristics they receive are very difficult. To produce maximum job satisfaction, the tasks or job characteristics given must be balanced with the employee's capacity and abilities.

Job characteristics are a job design model that shows how work is carried out in relation to the job duties and responsibilities delegated to an employee. (Elbandiansyah, 2019). The characteristics of excessive work received by employees is one of the factors that must be considered by companies to manage quality human resources. So that employees can get harmony in their work and if they are given a task, they can complete it well and well. If the job characteristics given exceed the limits of an employee's abilities, the employee's job satisfaction will certainly not be optimal.

Work involvement or job involvement is defined as a measure of the extent to which individuals psychologically favor their work and consider the level of Work Competency achieved to be important as self-esteem (Robbins et al., 2017).

According to (Afriani, 2017) work involvement is an employee who has high work involvement in his work, characterized by the employee having high concern for his work, a feeling of psychological attachment to the work he does and a strong belief in his ability to complete the work.

The four indicators for measuring work engagement are:

- 1) Response to work;
- 2) Behavior involving oneself in work
- 3) Sense of responsibility for work
- 4) Feelings about unfinished work and absenteeism. (Robbins et al., 2017).

Competency is the ability to carry out or perform a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitudes required by the job (Wibowo, 2016).

Competencies are the underlying characteristics of a person relating to the effectiveness of individual Work Competencies in their work or the basic characteristics of individuals which have a causal or causal relationship with the Work Competencies which

are used as a reference, effective or excellent or superior Work Competencies in the workplace or in certain situations, (Phitsa et al., 2015).

According to (Wibowo, 2016) states that competence is the basic basis of people's characteristics and indicates how to behave or think, equalize situations, and support for a long period of time. There are five types of competency characteristics, namely as follows:

- 1) A motive is something a person consistently thinks or desires that causes an action. Motives encourage, direct, and select behavior toward certain actions or goals.
- 2) Traits are physical characteristics and consistent responses to situations or information. Reaction speed and eye sharpness are physical characteristics of a fighter pilot's competence.
- 3) Self-concept is a person's attitudes, values, or self-image. Self-confidence is people's belief that they can be effective in almost any situation and is part of people's self-concept.
- 4) Knowledge is the information that people have in a specific field. Knowledge is a complex competency. Scores on knowledge tests often fail to predict job performance because they fail to measure knowledge and skills in the way they are actually used on the job.
- 5) Skills are the ability to perform certain physical or mental tasks. Mental competence or cognitive skills include analytical and conceptual thinking.

By understanding these conditions and phenomena, this research is directed at identifying the extent to which Work Engagement contributes to Employee Work Competence with Job Satisfaction as an intervening variable at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office, with the hope that the research results can provide insight and recommendations to improve employee work effectiveness.

The purpose of this research is to analyze and determine the influence of work involvement on the work competency of employees at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is quantitative associative clause research. This research was carried out at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office. This research was carried out from March 2024 to April 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018b) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The

population in this study were all employees of the general section of the Binjai City secretariat office, totaling 24 people with the following details:

Table 1. Total Population

Status	Amount
Civil servants	8
Non civil servant	16
Total	24

According to (Sugiyono, 2018b) the sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population. If the population is large, and it is impossible for researchers to study everything in the population, for example due to limited funds, energy and time, then researchers can use samples taken from that population. In this research the author used the entire population, namely the total number of employees as many as 24 people.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Work Competency

X = Work Engagement

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). According to (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013) the determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely Work Involvement (X), on the dependent variable, namely Work Competence (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the

influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Work Engagement	24	3.00	5.00	4.0625	,49040
Competence	24	2.80	5.00	4.5167	,53703
Valid N (listwise)	24				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess the Work Engagement and Work Competence of employees at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office to be above average, with mean values of 4.062 and 4.516 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.490 for Work Involvement and 0.537 for employee Work Competence), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have a fairly positive view of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for Work Involvement Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KK1	0.807 > 0.404	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KK2	0.630 > 0.404	0.001 < 0.05	Valid
KK3	0.842 > 0.404	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KK4	0.588 > 0.404	0.003 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the Work Engagement variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.404 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the indicators for the Work Engagement variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2018a).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Work Competency Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KOM1	0.487 > 0.404	0.016 < 0.05	Valid
KOM2	0.836 > 0.404	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM3	0.611 > 0.404	0.002 < 0.05	Valid
KOM4	0.655 > 0.404	0.001 < 0.05	Valid
KOM5	0.699 > 0.404	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on the employee Job Competency variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.404 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee Job Competency variable are valid, (Sugiyono, 2018a).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (α) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (α) value is > 0.61.

Table 5 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Work Engagement	0.683	4
Job competence	0.663	5

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (α) value of the employee Work Involvement and Work Competency variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

A This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	13,947	,947		4,167	,000
Work Engagement	,140	,232	,128	3,605	,002

a. Dependent Variable: Competence

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 13.947 + 0.140X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 13.947 means that if there is no work involvement, then there is an employee's work competency of 13.947 points. The Job Involvement regression coefficient is 0.140, meaning that Job Engagement influences an increase in employee Work Competence by 0.140 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,128a	,016	,228	,54459

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Engagement

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.228 or 22.80%, which means that Work Engagement has a low influence on employee Work Competence while the remaining 77.20% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of Work Involvement on the Work Competence of employees at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office

Ha: There is an influence of Work Involvement on the Work Competence of employees at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	13,947	,947		4,167	,000
Work Engagement	,140	,232	,128	3,605	,002

a. Dependent Variable: Competence

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is $3.605 > t$ table 1,710, with a significance value of $0.002 < 0.05$, thus it can be stated that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between Work Involvement on the Work Competence of employees at the Secretariat Office. Binjai City area.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of Job Involvement on Job Competence, this finding is in line with research results (Darmayasa & Puja Suasti, 2022) which show that there is a positive and significant influence between Job Engagement and Job Competence. This means improvements in Job Engagement and contributing to increased Job Competence.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of data analysis resulting from the research and discussion described above, it can be concluded that Work Involvement (interpersonal relationships) has a significant influence on Work Competence in the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office with a calculated t value of $3.605 > t$ table 1,710, and a significance value of $0.002 < 0.05$. These results indicate that if relationships between employees are improved, Job Competence tends to increase. The results of this research provide practical implications for management and improvement in the work environment to increase Work Competence through attention to these factors.

The results of the termination coefficient test show that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.228 or 22.80%, which means that Work Engagement has a low category influence on employee Work Competence while the remaining 77.20% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the results of the analysis and conclusions of this research, the following are several suggestions that can be given to the Regional Secretariat Office of Binjai City to improve employee Work Competence through increasing Work Involvement:

1. Institutions need to focus on improving relationships between employees to increase Job Engagement. This can be done by holding activities that support social interaction, such as team building, gatherings, and other events that encourage collaboration and communication. Additionally, it is important to create a friendly and supportive work environment, where employees feel comfortable sharing ideas and contributing.
2. Institutions need to hold ongoing training and development programs to improve employee work competency. Training that is structured and appropriate to job requirements will help employees develop the skills needed for better performance. Mentoring and coaching programs can also be implemented to provide direct guidance from more experienced employees.

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